

"ASSESSMENT OF LEAF LITTER DECOMPOSITION RATE OF IMPORTANT TREE SPECIES"

Mili Kirtikumar Shah^{1*}, S.W. Choudhari², V.B. Shambharkar³, S.D. Jadhao⁴,
H. K. Deshmukh⁵, S.S. Harne⁶, and Pritam R. Haldar⁷

mili_kirtikumar1002@gmail.com

1 & 7 PG Student, Department of Forestry, Dr. PDKV, Akola.

2, 3 & 5 Assistant Professor, Department of Forestry, Dr. PDKV, Akola.

4 Associate Professor, Soil Science, Dr. PDKV, Akola.

5 Professor & Head department of Forestry, Dr. PDKV, Akola, Maharashtra, India.

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Abstract

The study was carried out over the course of six months, from January 2025 to June 2025, and was an investigation about Assessment of leaf litter decomposition rate of important tree species which was carried out in the campus of Dr. Panjabrao Deshmukh Krishi Vidyapeeth, Akola. There were five species selected viz. *Pongamia pinnata*, *Terminalia arjuna*, *Eucalyptus teriticornis*, *Hardwickia binata*, and *Tectona grandis* and each species litter was consider as a separate individual treatment. CO₂ evolutions were employed as a metric to monitor and investigate the rates of decomposition of the chosen species. The Alkali trap method was used to carry out the decomposition in a laboratory setting. At 1, 7, 21, 28, 56, 84, and 112 days, the CO₂ evolutions were noted. There were six treatments (including control) and four replications in the randomised block design trial. Control was sample without organic matter (leaf litter) except soil. Nutrient composition of leaf litter (C, N, P, K) was also assessed. Over time, every species displayed a decreasing pattern of breakdown. *Tectona grandis* had the fastest rate of decomposition among the species studied, while *Eucalyptus teriticornis* had the slowest, with the order being *T. grandis* > *T. arjuna* > *H. binata* > *P. pinnata* > *E. teriticornis*. If such species is included in agroforestry models, some of these nutrients and organic matter would be utilised by the plants. The nutrients might support soil fertility sustainability, which is a significant phenomenon for agroforestry, restoration, and afforestation practices.

Keywords: Leaf litter, decomposition rate, CO₂ evolution, nutrients.

Introduction

It is important to research how forest tree residues break down in agroforestry for a number of reasons. Decomposition is the process by which microbes such as bacteria and fungus break down complex organic compounds into simpler ones. It occurs when trees in an ecosystem drop their leaves, branches, and other organic waste. By releasing nutrients back into the soil, this process enriches it and promotes the growth of other plants. Adding leaf litter increases the amount of organic carbon, microbial activity, and water-holding capacity by providing organic matter (Ngoran *et al.*, 2006, Bhalawe *et al.*, 2012). By guaranteeing the availability of nutrients for crops and trees, an understanding of this decomposition process aids in the efficient management of agroforestry systems.

A considerable proportion of organic material returns to the vegetation floor through litter fall, with leaves accounting for 70–90% of the total litter fall in various ecological settings. It is essential to the process of transmission. (Pande *et al.*, 2002). Soil characteristics and nutrient dynamics are significantly impacted by the decomposition of leaf litter from different tree species. As leaves fall to the ground, they break down and release nutrients that might affect microbial activity and soil fertility. Different tree species have leaves with different chemical compositions, carbon contents, and nutritional contents, which can affect how quickly the litter breaks down and how it affects the soil. According to Nivethadevi *et al.*, (2021), the addition and decomposition of leaf litter is a crucial biological process of nitrogen cycling and soil formation that sustains the activity of microfauna.

The rate at which nutrients such as potassium, phosphorus, and nitrogen are released into the soil can be ascertained. Maintaining soil fertility and productivity in agroforestry systems requires this understanding. These agroforestry processes replace the soil's fertility by adding nutrients (Yadav *et al.* 2008, Notaro *et al.* 2014). Additionally, it lessens the need for outside inputs by assisting in the decision-making process about fertilisation techniques. Thus the study was undertaken with the objectives: To study the decomposition rate of leaf litter of tree species viz. *Tectona grandis*, *Hardwickia binata*, *Pongamia pinnata*, *Terminalia arjuna* and *Eucalyptus teriticornis*.

Materials and Method**Study site**

The present study was conducted in the campus of Dr. Panjabrao Deshmukh Krishi Vidyapeeth, Akola, Maharashtra, in order to determine the decomposition rate of leaf litter and the soil properties of the plantation sites. Akola is 307.42 meters above mean sea level and located 20.6996° N, 77.0161° E. Under the several plantations chosen for the study, the conditions at the study location were basically the same. The climate of Akola is semi-arid. The average monthly maximum temperature in the hottest month, May, is 34.4°C. In comparison, the average monthly minimum temperature in December, which is the coldest month, is 8.4°C. The region receives 711.1 mm of rain annually on average. The monsoon season, which lasts from June to September, sees the most rainfall, while there is sporadic, erratic rainfall in January and February. The average daily evaporation can drop to 3.4 mm in December and exceed 6.1 mm in June. The average wind speed in June is between 4.7 km/h.

General tree parameters

Plantations were separated into four 10m x 10m sample plots, all of which were set up for biophysical measurements. Four sample plots (replications) were placed at each of the four corners of the chosen plantation, where each species of tree was treated as a single treatment. Tree height was measured by Ravi's altimeter (Chaturvedi and Khanna, 1981). Girth at breast height (GBH) at 1.37 m from the ground level was measured with the help of measuring tape.

Nutrient content in leaf litter

Leaf litter was gathered during the litter autumn season from every plantation location. The leaf litter of every species was shade-dried and maintained at 60 degrees Celsius in a dry air oven to preserve the ideal moisture content of plant residues. Its biochemical makeup and rate of decomposition were then examined. As recommended by AOAC (1995), the micro Kjeldahl method was used to measure the total N (%) of the leaf sample. The di-acid digestion extract and flame photometry method Piper (1966) were used to estimate the total K (%) of the leaf sample. Koeing and Johnson (1942) used the Vanadomolybdate-phosphoric acid yellow colour method to quantify total P (%). The Loss on Ignition approach was used to estimate Total C (%) (Flindt *et al.*, 2020).

Decomposition of leaf litter

There were six treatments (including control) and four replications in the randomised block design trial. Control was sample without organic

matter (leaf litter) except soil. The Alkali trap method (Zeng *et al.*, 2010) was used to observe and record the rate of decomposition and cumulative rate of decomposition at 1, 7, 21, 28, 56, 84, and 112 days while the sample was in an ex-situ laboratory. A 20 ml open plastic tube filled with 15 ml of 0.5 N Sodium hydroxide (NaOH) was hung inside the incubation flasks using an insulated wire strip in order to collect the CO₂ that was released. The 100g leaf litter of each species with 10% soil (i.e for 100g leaf litter 10g soil) and optimum moisture were kept in firmly sealed flasks at a controlled temperature of 27.5 ± 0.5 °C in a dark cabinet. Background CO₂ was taken into account by using a control jar that contained only 0.5 M NaOH and no soil or plant residues. A method modified from Bundy and Bremner (1972) was used to back-titrate with 0.5 N HCl after adding 3N Barium chloride in order to measure the amount of CO₂ absorbed by the NaOH in all six treatments and the blank at each sample interval. Freshly made NaOH was used at each sampling location to replace the NaOH tubes in the flasks that were not being sampled in order to prevent CO₂ saturation. The incubation flasks contained 100g leaf litter +10% soil (i.e for 100g leaf litter 10g soil) + Moisture 20-25% (Field capacity moisture content).

Statistical Analysis

The gathered data was statistically analysed using the RBD of the experiment. Simple statistical techniques such as analysis of variance (ANOVA), Panse and Sukhatme (1967), and comparison of the nutrient

Table 1 General tree parameters

Tree Species	Age of plantation (years)	Height (m)	GBH (cm)
<i>Tectona grandis</i>	45	14.43	70.33
<i>Hardwickia binata</i>	35	14.19	60.17
<i>Pongamia pinnata</i>	09	6.89	51.34
<i>Terminalia arjuna</i>	42	11.25	85.83
<i>Eucalyptus tereticornis</i>	07	16.97	32.29
S.E. (m) ±	-	0.15	2.56
C.D. (1%)	-	0.46	7.99

Nutrient content of leaf litter

Key nutrient contents in the leaf litter of five significant tree species are shown in Table 4, total carbon (C), total nitrogen (N), total phosphorus (P), and total potassium (K). For the values, percentages (%) are used.

It is evident from the data on total C that T5 (*E. tereticornis*) had the highest value (58.77 %), followed by T3 (*P. pinnata*) with the second-highest value (51.78 %), and T4 (*T. arjuna*) with the lowest value (41.58 %). The values (48.48 %) and (45.87 %) for T1 (*T. grandis*) and T2 (*H. binata*) respectively were moderate.

For each of the chosen significant tree species, the total N content varied considerably. With the greatest N content (2.43 %), T1 (*T. grandis*) appears to have nitrogen-rich leaf litter. The lowest N concentration (0.75

Table 2 Nutrient content of leaf litter

Treatment	Total C	Total N	Total P	Total K	C/N Ratio
	(%)				
T1 (<i>Tectona grandis</i>)	48.48	2.43	0.13	1.02	20.07
T2 (<i>Hardwickia binata</i>)	45.87	1.14	0.22	0.78	39.07
T3 (<i>Pongamia pinnata</i>)	51.78	0.82	0.30	0.89	62.06
T4 (<i>Terminalia arjuna</i>)	41.58	1.56	0.16	0.92	24.10
T5 (<i>Eucalyptus tereticornis</i>)	58.77	0.75	0.09	0.70	64.59
S.E. (m) ±	1.371	0.19	0.02	0.03	3.83
C.D. (1%)	4.271	0.60	0.07	0.09	11.94

Phosphorous concentrations in various species vary, as shown by the data given in Table 4. T3 (*P. pinnata*) had the highest value (0.30%), whereas T2 (*H. binata*) had the second-highest value (0.22 %). T1 (*T. grandis*)

content (Total N, P, and K) in the leaf litter of species taken into consideration in the experiment were used to analyse and compare the variation in the decomposition rate of leaf litter.

Results and Discussion

General Tree Parameters

Table 1 displays the tree growth data, which were used as a baseline to understand the condition of five significant tree species' plantations. The observations focused on the plantation's age, mean height and girth at breast height (GBH) These species were (T1) *Tectona grandis*, (T2) *Hardwickia binata*, (T3) *Pongamia pinnata*, (T4) *Terminalia arjuna* and (T5) *Eucalyptus tereticornis*. Although *Eucalyptus tereticornis* is the youngest at 7 years old, it has the largest mean height (16.97 m) compared to 45-year-old *T. grandis*, suggesting strong early growth. *Eucalyptus* trees have the highest mean height because they grow more fast than other tree species, according to Troup (2008). The species with the lowest mean height is *Pongamia pinnata* (6.89 m). Furthermore, the findings show that *T. arjuna* (85.83 cm) has the highest mean GBH at age 42, followed by *T. grandis* (70.33 cm). Tree height and GBH are the growth variables that are most impacted by site conditions and the different growth behaviours of trees. Height and diameter have been said to be correlated with volume and, thus, biomass (FSI, 1996; Jha, 1999 and Kiyono *et al.*, 2010).

%) is seen in T5 (*E. tereticornis*). The values are similar to what Bhalawe *et al.* (2013) found. Despite being leguminous, T2 (*H. binata*) and T3 (*P. pinnata*) exhibit lower N content than T1 (*T. grandis*). This variation may be influenced by species and age. According to research, there is a general pattern in plant nutrition where nutrient concentration changes with tree age (Barker and Pilbeam, 2006; Yuan *et al.*, 2007). In the case of T1 (*T. grandis*), Moya *et al.* (2012) state that N ranges from 1.7 to 2.3 %, which is consistent with the findings of this investigation. The content of N was higher than other nutrients examined in the study. Studies have generally shown that tropical climates have higher nitrogen concentrations and more litter fall, according to Eguakun and Job (2018).

exhibits a phosphorus concentration of (0.13 %). This figure is similar to what Bhalawe *et al.* (2013) found. Compared to T1, T4 (*T. arjuna*) has a

greater phosphorus concentration (0.16%). T5 (*E. tereticornis*) had the lowest value (0.09 %).

According to the K content data in Table 4, T1 (*T. grandis*) has the highest potassium level of any treatment at (1.02 %). When it came to potassium concentration, T4 (*T. arjuna*) had the second-highest figure (0.92 %), followed by T3 (*P. pinnata*) (0.89 %). T5 (*E. tereticornis*) had the lowest potassium concentration (0.70%), whereas T2 had a substantially greater potassium content (0.78 %) than T5 (*E. tereticornis*). The results in T1 (*T. grandis*) are similar to those of Bhalawe *et al.* (2013).

Decomposition of leaf litter

The alkali trap method was used to study the leaf litter decomposition of *Tectona grandis*, *Hardwickia binata*, *Pongamia pinnata*, *Terminalia arjuna*, and *Eucalyptus tereticornis* in ex-situ for 112 days, from February 19/02/25 to June 11/06/25. CO₂ production was used to quantify the rates of leaf litter decomposition. Chintu *et al.* (2004) used a similar methodology in their investigation. Therefore, as proposed by Smith *et al.* (1993), CO₂-C evolution is a sensitive indicator of the rate of decomposition.

It is evident from Table 6 and Figure 1 that for all treatments, the rate of CO₂ evolution over time generally reduced. This is frequently observed in soil or decomposition studies, when microbial activity is initially high and then decreases as easily decomposable organic waste is ingested. With the highest initial rate and a sharp decline over time, T1 (*T. grandis*) exhibits the steepest overall reduction. Additionally, T4 (*T. arjuna*) exhibits a sharp drop following the initial time point, suggesting a quicker rate of breakdown and substrate consumption. T2 (*H. binata*) exhibits moderate to high starting rates with a consistent drop at the same time. But compared to other treatments, T3 (*P. pinnata*) exhibits the most consistent CO₂ evolution across time, holding higher rates for longer. Furthermore, T6 (control) continuously exhibits the lowest CO₂ evolution across the whole period, while T5 (*E. tereticornis*) has moderate starting rates and tends to diminish gradually.

The abrupt reduction in T4 (*T. arjuna*) following T1 (*T. grandis*) across the chosen tree species and the control sample indicates that this treatment contains easily decomposable organic matter that promotes intense initial microbial activity. However, the rate reduces sharply once this labile carbon is consumed. This trend is typical of treatments involving high-quality organic inputs that microbes consume quickly. The lowest carbon evolution in T5 (*E. tereticornis*) began at a reasonable starting point and steadily declined, suggesting a lower rate of decomposition of the species' leaf litter. The disintegration may have been postponed by the essential oils and other chemical components of the leaves. According to Swift *et al.* (1979), it is known that the rate of decomposition of litters produced by different plant species under comparable environmental conditions differs because of differences in the physical and chemical features of the litters. Additionally, de Moral and Muller (1969) assert that the slow rate of eucalypt litter decomposition may be due to the presence of volatile terpenes and polyphenols in the leaves. By inhibiting the activity of microbial enzymes, these substances are known to slow down the pace of decomposition (Benoit and Starkey, 1968). The rough texture and waxy coating of eucalypt leaves are additional factors that could affect decomposition.

Moreover, the kinetics of litter breakdown are generally species-dependent and influenced by the chemical makeup of the litter, according to Ashton *et al.* (1999) and Sangha *et al.* (2006). Additionally, trees that are good at biological N fixing are known to have low C:N ratios and a high initial N content, which encourages the rapid breakdown of litter (Sandhu *et al.*, 1990). However, the breakdown rates of leguminous species such as T2 (*H. binata*) and T3 (*P. pinnata*) were slow and moderate, respectively, in the current study. This is consistent with the results of Sandhu *et al.* (1990), who found that the pace at which the leaf

litter of another tree legume degraded in Varanasi was slower than that of teak. These findings confirm that lignin degradation is significantly lower in nitrogen-rich litters than in nitrogen-poor ones (Berg *et al.*, 1982). Furthermore, the high C:N influenced the decomposition rate by maintaining the CO₂ evolution for a longer period of time than T1 (*T. grandis*) due to the high carbon and nitrogen contents in the leaf litter of T2 (*H. binata*) and T3 (*P. pinnata*) (shown in Table 4).

Conclusion

It can be concluded that T1 (*Tectona grandis*) demonstrated the fastest rate of leaf litter decomposition among significant tree species. This species can be suggested for agroforestry methods due to its ability to improve soil organic carbon status, nitrogen content, and high commercial value in the lumber industry, in addition to its rapid rate of decomposition. The additional nutrients might help maintain soil fertility, which is a crucial aspect of afforestation and land management success. The species under study showed the fastest rate of decomposition in order *T. grandis* > *T. arjuna* > *H. binata* > *P. pinnata* > *E. tereticornis* while *Eucalyptus tereticornis* had the slowest.

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Table 3 Rate of CO₂ evolution from decomposed leaf litter of important tree species

Treatment	Day of Decomposition –CO ₂ evolution (mg per 100 gm)						
	1 st	7 th	21 st	28 th	56 th	84 th	112 th
T1(<i>Tectona grandis</i>)	536.68	504.03	384.63	297.63	221.88	122.08	102.20
T2(<i>Hardwickia binata</i>)	482.00	452.59	370.05	214.50	208.30	118.78	101.35
T3(<i>Pongamia pinnata</i>)	450.25	439.15	400.68	356.48	324.70	237.80	217.25
T4(<i>Terminalia arjuna</i>)	554.25	491.18	420.85	289.80	250.30	219.48	190.14
T5(<i>Eucalyptus tereticornis</i>)	314.00	275.75	221.48	197.58	139.33	98.25	59.53
*T6 (control)	252.50	232.75	63.00	41.00	35.25	18.55	16.75

*: is a control sample i.e. incubation flask with no leaf litter and only soil.

Figure 1 Rate of CO₂ Evolution (mg per 100g)